

Step-by-Step Protocol

Minimum Setup:

- 1 researcher as supervisor on experiment site (+1 researcher for post-experiment coding)
- 1 lab computer with test software installed and prepared
→ check file “Experiment Guide EN.pdf” for an example setup with Citavi
- software for screen recordings (e.g. OBS)
- 1 correct and 1 erroneous tutorial video for the test software
→ check files “Video Tutorial Correct No Audio CC.mp4” and “Video Tutorial Incorrect No Audio CC.mp4” for example videos for Citavi
- 1 sheet with instructions for watching the (erroneous) tutorial
→ check file “Tutorial Video Instructions EN.pdf” for an example scenario with Citavi
- 1 sheet with instructions for the experiment tasks within the test software
→ check file “Task Instructions EN.pdf” for an example scenario with Citavi
- 1 information sheet for debriefing the participants after the experiment
→ check file “Deception and Debriefing.pdf” for an example scenario with Citavi
- drawing and writing material for mental model sketches
- pre- and post-experiment questionnaires as needed

Experiment Walkthrough:

1. before the experiment, prepare the experiment site
→ check file “Experiment Guide EN.pdf” for an example setup with Citavi
2. enter the study participant and have them read and sign all necessary legal documents
3. start the experiment conduction
→ check file “Experiment Guide EN.pdf” for an example walkthrough with Citavi
4. after the experiment, debrief the participant and, if applicable, hand out compensation
5. renew the experiment site for the next participant (step 1)

6. analyze the mental model sketches, screen recording footage and any additional data (e.g. from observations and questionnaires)
 - 6.1 did the participant sketch their mental model in accordance with the tutorial?
→ if the sketch includes elements of erroneous instructions, we can assume that the flawed mental model was successfully induced
 - 6.2 did the participant follow the tutorial?
→ if the participant followed erroneous instructions, we can assume that the flawed mental model was successfully induced
 - 6.3 did the participant show or express a need for explanations during their task attempts?
→ if the participant followed erroneous instructions (6.2) AND showed a need for explanation, we can assume that the mental model conflict was successfully induced